

Depression Screening in a Skilled Nursing Facility

Wanting Tan, DNP, PMHNP-BC, RN; Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN, CEN
Nnenna Weathers, PhD, PMHNP, FNP

Background

Depression

- 46.3% depression rate in Skilled Nursing Facilities (SNFs)
- Depressed adults experience increased risk of comorbidities and mortality
- Depression often co-occurs and worsens symptoms of dementia

Depression Screening Tools

- Recommend depression screening with Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ)-2
 - if positive, follow-up with PHQ-9 or Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS-15)
- Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD)
 - Considers responses from patient and caregiver.
 - Detects depression better in patients with cognitive impairment than both PHQ-9 and GDS-15

AIMS

To enhance depression identification in SNF residents with cognitive impairment by implementing and evaluating a standardized, evidence-based depression screening protocol

Setting/Sample

- Setting: 105-bed SNF at Whittier, CA
- Sample:
 - Verbal
 - Fluent in English
 - Written consent for participation by resident or their Legally Authorized Representative (LAR)

Conceptual Model

Model for Improvement

Questions answered in order:

1. Improve depression identification
2. More depression identified than at admission
3. Implement depression screening protocol

Plan

- Phase One: Implement PHQ-2 depression screening by staff
- Phase Two: Implement CSDD for residents with cognitive impairment

Do

- Obtained facility approval
- Phase One implemented as policy change prior to project start
- Obtained Institutional Review Board approval
- Implements Phase Two as part of project
- Recruitment of participant and obtaining consents
- Collection of data

Study

- Analyzed data

Act

- Summarized findings
- Formulated recommendations for future implementations

Results

PHQ-2 screening:

58 screened, 19 positive, one unable to screen, = 32.76% positivity rate, unspecified increase in referrals

CSDD screening:

6 qualified, 3 LAR refusal, 1 LAR lost contact for written consent, 2 participants screened

Resident	Existing MDD DX (No = 0; Yes = 1)	Existing antidepressant use (No = 0; Yes = 1)	PHQ-2 Score (0-6)	BIMS Score (0-15)	PHQ-9 Score (0-27)	CSDD - Resident (0-38)	CSDD - Caregiver (0-38)
1	0	0	0	4	0	0	4
2	1	1	6	11	16	16	4

- Resident 1: no previous hx, severe dementia, all tests showed no Major Depressive Disorder (MDD)
- Resident 2: had previous hx and med use, moderate dementia, all test except CSDD caregiver version showed positive score for MDD

Limitations

Small sample size

- COVID-19 lead to hospitalizations and many discharged for safety concerns
- Half of residents were not eligible
 - Non-English speakers
 - Communication deficits

Difficulty in obtaining written consent

- Travel restrictions limited ability to reach and obtain written consent from LAR
- High rate of LAR refusals

Discussion

- PHQ-2 screening improved depression identification upon admission with additional mental health referrals
- Unable to make conclusions from this sample regarding CSDD
- Discrepancy between resident CSDD and nursing staff caregiver CSDD scores similar to other studies
- Difficulty in obtaining consent presents as main obstacle to implementation research on patients with cognitive impairments.
 - Similar to 1992 Congressional assessment conclusion about special unit research in US
 - Many depression screening test outside of US

Recommendations

- PHQ- 2 standard screening should be implemented in all SNFs
- Expansion of project implementation to other SNFs is required to determine if CSDD is an efficient test.
 - Apparent discrepancy between caregiver and residents
 - To reach large enough population to make definitive conclusions